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The Effect of Method Pedagogy and English Teaching Learning

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Abstract

The end of the 20th century, methodology was no longer the determining factor of whether language teaching was successful or unsuccessful in mainstream settings. In the 1990s, some ELT practitioners, teachers and theorists expressed their unhappiness with approaches and techniques when the concept of method was questioned. The term "methodology era" refers to this. On the other hand, methodology is defined as avoiding rigorous methodological discussions to determine the most successful teaching approach that incorporates the best viewpoints and methods, as well as the role of practitioners in lesson preparation and instructional design. In addition, the effect of methodology pedagogy on English language learning strategies because methodology teacher education programs require teachers to consider developing critical thinking skills, acknowledging their voice and vision, and pursuing goodness through dialogic meaning-making, these programs have a significant impact on teachers. In order to highlight the value of evaluating pre-existing theories and notions that might be understood in light of publications that spark discussion, this research combines descriptive and library research investigations. The purpose of this study is to find out how methodology pedagogy affects English teaching Learning.

Keyword: ELT instruction; methodology pedagogy; Pasca- method.

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INTRODUCTION

Through ups and downs. In the early and mid-20th century, researchers in the field of English language teaching (ELT) proposed various methods and approaches. Practitioners have developed a range of language teaching methods and approaches that can serve as effective frameworks for successful language teaching. That I know, there is no one-size-fits-all approach. Regardless, foreign language teaching has proven successful. Teaching methods or techniques (Brown, 2000). besides. As the history of language teaching records, some approaches and methods are clear. They are difficult to understand and apply, lack clear practical applications, require specialized training, and require significant changes in teachers' practices and beliefs, all of which have the potential for widespread application. Reduce sex appeal (Allwright, 1991)

The majority of language teachers had given up on methodology as the primary determinant of a lesson's success or failure by the late 20th century. Some ELT practitioners, instructors, and theorists started to voice their displeasure with the approach and technique as the system's core assumptions were questioned in the 1990s. This is where the phrase "post-method era" originated. Experts refer to the unrecorded origins of the post technique as eclecticism (Fat, 2015). A post-method condition questions whether the concept of a technique is accurate. Stated otherwise, Kumaravadivelu (1994) developed a post-method pedagogical in response to the most effective English teaching strategy that can be freed from the limitations of method-based instruction. Post-method pedagogy looks at instructional resources for real-world communication in second language (L2) classrooms and tries to help students become more fluent and accurate language users. According to this viewpoint, students are encouraged to reach their full potential and are acknowledged as participants in a cooperative endeavor (Kumaravadivelu, 2001). Providing classroom teachers with new possibilities frees ELT practitioners and professionals from many of the constraints imposed by method notions and transforms classroom instruction. However, the post-pedagogy method has its own limitations and is sometimes criticized. (Akbari, 2008; Bell, 2003).

In order to find the most effective ways to educate, post-method is defined by the giving up of solely methodological disputes and the consideration of practitioners' perspectives and roles in the planning and creation of instructional materials. Language teachers nowadays need to search for the most effective ways and tactics to broaden their teaching repertoire, rather than concentrating on the most appropriate language teaching approach. as opposed to well-known and widely used paradigms of language teaching practice, which are typified by enforcing methodological issues rather than empowering individual teachers to choose the most effective teaching strategies on their own. As a result, we are becoming more aware of the personal journey of the language instructor. With regard to post-method learning, Kumaravadivelu (2006) suggests three different kinds of guidelines or precepts: The dimensions for peculiarities include expertise, practicality, and potential; post-method pedagogy stresses the significance of local context, or "situational understanding," as Kumaravadivelu puts it (p 171). This metric indicates that L2 managers and policymakers are cognizant of local circumstances and are inclined to devise strategies that support efficient instruction (Mus, I, 2024; Rahman, F, 2023; Tiara, A, 2022; Zikrullah, M., & Azhari, A, 2024).

Overseas students must learn English, particularly in Indonesia. Maduwu's (2016) argument, which notes that English is widely spoken, supports this as well. English language proficiency is therefore essential, if not required. Learning English is still challenging, if not terrifying, for the majority of Indonesians. In the course of the learning process, the instructor

might instruct and provide instructional resources. Among other roles, he ought to play the roles of advisor, instructor, researcher, organizer, manager, programmer, designer, and diagnostician (Illich, 2000). To be more precise, the instructor facilitates and partners with student communication. Teaching English is challenging, of course. To assist students with different levels of ability and expertise in understanding the information covered in each session, teachers need to use a range of tactics. Teachers also need to exercise creativity in the materials they choose and in inspiring their students to learn. Teachers thus need to modify a number of their methods in order to support students' learning. Learning strategies and tactics can improve learning in a number of ways, including ease of use, speed, enjoyment, independence, effectiveness, and adaptability to new circumstances (Oxford, 2001).

Instead of focusing on a small number of tactics and procedures, creative teachers use a wide range of strategies and talents to match the demands and learning styles of each student. Teachers must employ a range of tactics when teaching reading in order to raise students' motivation to learn English, especially reading, and to help them become better readers. An English instructor can increase the efficiency of the classroom process by implementing the right tactics. Kumaravadivelu (2006) asserts that the approaches used are artificial rather than based in their classrooms. This is because they haven't shown up yet. Their conception and development have been informed by actual teaching and learning experiences. Certain theories of language assert that they have no bearing on the situations that educators and learners encounter in language classrooms. Consequently, these approaches lose their relevance when used in the classroom because they fail to satisfy the needs of the students, who require that they comprehend and draw from their culture as a source of knowledge and inspiration for introspection. Frischknecht et al. (2007) state that the "methods are not based on empirical studies, but they are too artful.

Students who have studied English in the classroom for a long time lack the information and abilities needed to take advantage of the language's communicative potential. The significance of giving students communication opportunities has been discussed (Ellis, 2008). In the L2 classroom, post-method pedagogy looks at instructional strategies that support real-world communication and help students improve both their fluency and verbal accuracy. Students are urged to make the most of their abilities and are regarded as partners in a cooperative endeavor. In Brown (2001). In a similar vein, Hamer (2001) reviews the language-related skills that must be acquired as well as the frequency at which "communicative language teaching" (CLT) incorporates various viewpoints. (Doughty & Long, 2008).

METHOD

This research was adapted from Suhaimi (2022). A literature study research methodology is used in this investigation. In a literary study, information is gathered through reading and taking notes, and then the information is processed using the predetermined concepts. and do a study of theories in order to identify a concept using the approach of classifying the theory and research into a concept after studying the categorical portion of the theory. The steps involved are collecting theoretical data from multiple literatures, processing it into concepts, and analyzing the emerging phenomenon in the field of education. Next, carry out in-depth research and analysis to identify solutions for the issues raised.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

The three main symbols of post-method pedagogy are the learner, the teacher, and the teacher educators. In postmethod pedagogy, the student is proactive and independent (Kumaravadivelu 2006), dividing autonomous learning into two categories: academic and communications services. In 2001, he proposed three kinds of autonomous learning: intellectual, sociological, and communications services.

Kumaravadivelu claims that the scholar approach is a limited vision that aims to give the student knowledge to know, but the liberatory perspective expands this to include the capacity to simultaneously learn and release. He characterizes learning as applying appropriate strategies to accomplish goals. By using the right strategies, learners can assess and maximize their learning methods. Students can be more involved when they have scholarly liberty, and when they use advanced social method software and computers to develop their critical thinking skills. Liberatory autonomy thereby actively promotes students' self- and social-reflection, learning community formation, and opportunities for inquiry and choice. As a result, students will be more prepared to handle problems in the classroom. But the help of others, especially their professors, will be necessary for them to succeed in this.

With post-method pedagogy, the instructor is viewed as an independent educator. This essential right to autonomy is the cornerstone of post-method education (Kumaravadivelu, 2006, p. 179). Post-method pedagogy recognizes the teacher's prior knowledge and understanding as well as their capacity for independent learning and instruction. It also assists the teacher in creating a contextual approach for their own instruction, analyzing and assessing the instructional acts of others, initiating classroom change, and evaluating the results of such modifications (Wallace, 1991). The capacity for instructional design can only improve when the teacher desires and is driven to uphold a reasonable level of autonomy. The instructor needs to draw from his prior and growing personal experience of education and teaching in order to overcome the constrictive notion of method. This understanding includes both the integration of physical and cognitive thought in addition to specialist classroom management. It appears as a consequence of persistent efforts. Because post-method pedagogy assumes that teachers will eventually acquire their own unique exercise perspective as a result of their own personal expertise (Kumaravadivelu, 2006).

The objective of the postmethod educator is to create environments where teacher educators can acquire the authority and independence they need to reflect on and draw lessons from their unique educational experiences, and in some situations, to transform such personal tales into teaching materials (Kumaravadivelu, 2006, p. 182). Communication channels facilitate conversation between student teachers and educators through a series of dialogic interactions. They are exchanging ideas all the time. Subsequently, the educators will demonstrate their readiness to integrate the concepts, viewpoints, and practical knowledge of the student teachers into the educational process. Ultimately, the entire approach to teacher education reduces to reflection and fulfillment.

Furthermore, autonomy is a distinguishing feature of postmethod era instructors (Kumaravadivelu, 2006). regarded as a postmethod pioneer. This is demonstrated by the teacher and indicates their expertise and confidence in creating and putting their theory into practice. One of them plays a crucial function as a postmethod autonomic sign educator, especially in the context of reflexive language instruction. Language teachers must engage in

introspective and analytical reflection on the qualities of their students in order to develop effective teaching and evaluation strategies. This entails assessing how their responsibilities, identities, prejudices, and culture influence how they view the needs and strengths of English language learners. In the post-method era, teacher autonomy will be as successful as it sounds. From the perspective of traditional language teaching, there is hope in the autonomous role of the teacher in the postmethod era. As a result, educators are better able to design reflective lessons, which is important when it comes to putting new ideas into practice and determining how they will affect students.

One of the main components of postmethod is the development of customized strategies and techniques that correspond with classroom-specific situations. When teachers are only provided top-down curriculums, instruction becomes more artificial and mechanical than organic. Educators are also deprived of the chance to rework curricula, turning them into passive recipients of information that is promptly transmitted to students, ensuring that their education is reduced to a predetermined path of ideas and doctrines. A "feeling of plausibility" is necessary for teachers, according to Prabhu (1990), if they are to enhance the learning process.

As a result, Kumaravadivelu (2001) argued that teachers and students shouldn't be thought of as mindless machines and that this kind of preservice education is useless. Moreover, the development of second language proficiency does not require the systematization of linguistic input or the optimization of exercise, but rather the establishment of dialogue-based environments in which learners participate. According to Prabhu (1990), teachers who employ their sense of credibility create a relationship in the classroom. To promote effective learning, teachers might conduct in-depth investigations into problems and work with students to develop and apply various explanations. Taking all of this into consideration, language instructors' perceptions of their own plausibility might only work in language classrooms if they are grounded in the experiences of post method pedagogy. Additionally, teachers will lose this sense of believability if they employ particular strategies that make their teaching seem more "mechanical" than "real" (Prabhu, 1990).

Additionally, the pedagogical approach in particular has to be vital to any post-method. For language pedagogy to be effective, it needs to be appropriate for a given group of teachers instructing a given group of students pursuing a given set of goals in a certain institution setting firmly rooted in a particular sociocultural context. Essentially, the idea behind the hermeneutical Elliott (1993) asserts that effective education cannot be developed without a comprehensive understanding of a particular context, nor can it be managed without a general improvement in the circumstances.

According to Kumaravadivelu (2003b), Both global and micro activities are part of the language learning post-method conceptual strategy. He clarifies Macro strategies are basic ideas derived from historical, conceptual, factual, and individual insights into the process of teaching and learning second languages. A macro plan is a broad framework that teaches teachers how to create demand-specific, location-specific micro strategies or how to provide teaching.

Ten macro strategies are offered by the strategy framework; they are all expressed practically and lack any prescriptive elements. They are listed below: (1) Boost your odds of learning. In this approach, teaching is seen as a means of generating and applying learning opportunities. The educator is viewed as a provider of learning opportunities for pupils as well as a learner who is being developed by the instructor. (2) Diminish mismatch of perception. This method places a strong emphasis on identifying any possible perceptual mismatches between

student viewpoints, educator aims, and interpretations. (3) Negotiating interactions is made simple. This method describes meaningful student-teacher interactions in the classroom when students are allowed and encouraged to start conversations and offer ideas instead of just responding or reacting. (4) Promote self-directed learning. The Strategy focuses on giving students the resources they require to direct and monitor their own learning in order to help them make informed study decisions. According to Forster, language sensitivity is placed eighth. This approach includes any attempt to get students to focus on formal and functional aspects of their L2 to raise the expressiveness level required for L2 learning. (6) Permit intuitive heuristics to function. The method places a strong emphasis on providing students with rich textual material so they can recognize and comprehend the fundamental ideas that govern conversational and grammatical usage. (7) Set up contextual language input. This method focuses on the ways that word choice and use are influenced by linguistic, extralinguistic, situational, and extra-situational factors. (8) Include linguistic skills. This macro technique highlights the need to integrate language skills that have traditionally been separated and grouped into four categories: literature, writing, talking, hearing, and writing. (9) Preserve your social standing. This method emphasizes how crucial it is for the teacher to comprehend the socio-political, financial, and academic settings used for L2 instruction and learning. (10) Develop social awareness: This method highlights how important it is to see students as cultural agents. to encourage students to participate in a teaching strategy that highlights their strong points.

To accomplish particular macro-strategic objectives, the above-described macrostrategies which are broad fundamental teaching principles must be put into practice in the classroom through micro-strategies. Multiple microstrategies can be included in a single macro plan. "Classroom practices" that work toward the bigger strategy's objectives are called microstrategies. The local education and learning circumstances dictate the many kinds of microstrategies. "The options are virtually limitless." (In 2006, Kumaravadivelu) Microstrategies are impacted by a variety of factors, including institutional resources, curriculum objectives, learner requirements, wants, and deficits, as well as general language proficiency and knowledge levels at the national, regional, or local levels. Kumaravadivelu puts learner autonomy and learning preferences fourth, intense teacher-student interactions third, learner training and perception second, and out-of-class chances first. Linguistic use and recognition come in fifth and sixth place, while contextualization of linguistic input comes in seventh. Utilizing all types of natural resources is the eighth. Generally speaking, Kumaravadivelu gives a thorough overview of how to create workable microstrategies while abiding by the corresponding macrostrategies in a certain scenario.

Furthermore, the history of language instruction demonstrates that some strategies and tactics are hard to comprehend and put into practice, lack a clear practical application, call for specialized training, and have a big impact on the behaviors and beliefs of teachers. Some required adjustment, therefore it was unlikely that they would spread (Allwright, 1991). However, the idea behind this method was heavily contested in the 1990s for a number of reasons, and some of the generic path concept's unspoken drawbacks were discovered. In the 1990s, there was a constant flow of critical thought within the profession on the nature and use of methods. Academics like Pennycook (1989), Allwright (1991), Prabhu (1990), and Stern (1992) cautioned language instructors not only against embracing dubious methods mindlessly but also against the concept of method itself. (Kumaravadivelu, 2006).

The post-method age of English instruction places a focus on a number of earlier approaches, including audiolingualism, total physical response, the silent way, and the natural approach. However, language education in the post-method period no longer revolves around concerns rather than technique, since the main focus of language teaching professionals has turned to finding more effective methods of language teaching, with the majority focusing on the research of specific methods.

In the post-method period, the instructor needs to devise a plan that is inextricably linked to the previous approach and does not introduce any new techniques. However, the approach speaks of meaningful classroom exchanges between students and teachers, where students are free to bring up subjects and start conversations rather than just responding or reacting. This indicates that the teacher's role in fostering classroom interaction is not just repetitive. Various traditional teaching strategies are included in centered learning. As a result, in this period of post-method education, language instructors and others must focus more on the requirements of the students than on the teacher.

However, Brown stated in Richard and Renandya (2002) in (Khafidhoh, 2017) that the reason why methodologies in language education have disappeared over time is that what is visible is the strategy:

1. Prescriptive methods make far too many assumptions about a context before it is ever established. Their potential relevance to actual situations is unduly broad.
2. Generally speaking, methods are somewhat distinct at the beginning of a language course and converge at the end. In their tiny rings of whispers, throughout the first few discrete sets of experience. Speech to their ears. But after a few weeks, this classroom could look just like any other. learner-focused curriculum.
3. In the past, it is estimated that scientific quantification could assess methods experimentally and determine which is best. There will never be an empirical validation of language pedagogy quite like this.
4. Current studies on the politics and power of teaching English have revealed that methods have evolved into linguistic imperialism directed toward the helpless and weak.

In recent years there is not good method to apply in the language teaching process but it is on the development of class assignments with activities that really are consistent with what we know about second language learning, as well as activities that are suited for the characteristics of the class itself.

Post-Method Pedagogy's Impact on English Learning Strategies Teachers need to consider the post-method teacher education program, which makes it particularly influential. the significance of acknowledging the voice and vision of the teacher, the necessity of developing their critical thinking skills, and the caution in accomplishing either through dialogic meaning formation. Because modern educational programs treat educators as experts and knowledge producers and practicing teachers as understanding clients, teachers have an obligation to influence and assist pupil educators in realizing the imbalances in the post-method strategies that they enable teacher candidates to express their ideas through an electronic journal where they can write down and share their political opinions, perceptions, and knowledge about language learning and teaching from the beginning to the end of their education with other teacher candidates.

Additionally, methodology pedagogy will have a better effect on a wider variety of teacher preparation. It is imperative that novice educators acquire the self-assurance required to engage with children and impart techniques and strategies for instructing them. Furthermore, a teacher will start to create his own method or teaching style as he gains expertise and experience. which describes a well-known but unique method or approach that embodies the instructor's unique values, experiences, and views are all instances of opinions. Learn about aspiring experts as they travel from using methods and approaches to creating and using their own unique set of analytical skills.

These days, pragmatic pedagogy has taken center stage instead of teaching transmission models to students and instructors alike. the need to create strategies to help teachers and students engage in the learning process (Pani, 2004) (Arikan, 2006). In developing a plan, it is necessary to investigate and interview each teacher to comprehend how the approach operates and how the teacher strives to implement it. A greater understanding of the post-method stage has led to the development of creative curricula, such as educator education programs, both inside and outside of schools. The goal is to help teachers of English become more adept at creating context-sensitive pedagogical knowledge, so that they may reflect on their own work and put their theories into practice.

Additionally, post-method pedagogy will have a better effect on a wider variety of teacher preparation. Gaining the self-assurance necessary to approach pupils and impart knowledge and techniques for teaching is crucial for novice educators. Additionally, as a teacher develops experience and skill, he will start to develop his own unique approach, often known as his personal manner of teaching. This approach or technique is well-known but unique, representing the instructor's unique experiences, values, beliefs, and ideas. Thus, teacher education and development programs must exist in the gap between these periods. Explore aspiring masters as they go from applying methods and approaches to creating and using their own toolkit of methodological perspectives and methods.

Language instruction has refocused on the teacher with the demise of methodology and the rise of post-method debate. Since only teachers are able to carry on the promises of post-methods, post-method education greatly depends on them (Ahmadian & Erfanrad, 2014). Because it acknowledges autonomy, agency, and mediated learning in addition to the teacher's function as a meaning builder, it is both perceptive and optimistic (Hosseini, Rashidi & Rasti, 2015). Drawing from his background as a critical thinker, theorist, and practitioner, Kumaravadivelu (2003) made a compelling case for teachers to enable students to adhere to the curriculum. Instructors investigate innovative, socially realistic, and contextual approaches to teaching.

Instructors who employ the Post-Method ought to have faith in their capacity to cultivate past learning and a thoughtful teaching style. It addresses both institutional systems and everyday schooling. He thinks that the process of teaching reflectively is challenging. "It makes a big shift in the focus of our thoughts and actions" (p. 213), which includes challenging your own views on education and adopting a critical attitude toward oneself as an educator. (499).

In the post-method era, Khani and Darabi (2014) list the following new responsibilities for teachers: observers, theorists, practitioners, evaluators, and critical thinkers. Khatib and Fathi (2012) state that post-method pedagogy views teachers as independent in their delivery of instruction. Put a stop to your excessive concern over adapting your teaching strategies to the advice of outside specialists. It encourages of them to use their personal experiences as a

framework for instruction. Teachers must therefore be reflective and critical practitioners. As said by Tasnimi (2014), Skilled post-methods educators are autonomous thinkers who create their own theories of practice. To get the intended outcome, you must carefully evaluate their instructions and make any required adjustments. It is not appropriate for a reflective teacher to only communicate knowledge that has already been chosen.

In his discussion of the role of educators, Prabhu (1990) contended that for teachers to enhance the educational process, they need to possess a "sense of plausibility". Experience, involvement in teacher preparation programs, and other elements all add to greater relevance. According to Prabhu, each teacher has a different sense of effectiveness, and teaching only becomes fruitful when the teacher's sense of validity is heightened and they are actively participating in the learning process. "Improving trust in the classroom requires involving teachers' sense of plausibility," he says. (p 173). Furthermore, the method's merits are unrelated to this emotion. According to him, teachers' sense of believability can easily become stuck when they employ particular techniques. Their instructions therefore come out as more "mechanical" than "authentic."

A post-method teacher educator is defined by Kumaravadivelu (2001). The first step is to help student teachers comprehend the disparities that exist in the existing teacher education programs, which view student teachers as knowledge consumers and teacher educators as knowledge creators. It also facilitates the exchange of ideas, presumptions, and expectations between educators and students. In the classroom, trainee instructors exchange language, learning, and teaching skills. Subsequently, motivates educators to exercise critical thinking and integrate their own understanding with the skills they are acquiring. Additionally, it gives student teachers the chance to pick up fundamental skills and reinforces the presumptions of practice-based concepts. It teaches how to construct theory from experience, in other words. Instead of conducting research for the student's teacher, collaborate with them on it. Finally, describe the advantages and disadvantages of your area of expertise and assist you in locating that information in light of your teaching and learning environment.

Teachers in the post-method era need to be practitioners of theory. Putting a lot of emphasis on reflective instruction is necessary to solve issues in the classroom. Since there's no one right way, educators ought to reconsider how they grow. Contextualized Techniques to Optimize Educational Possibilities Her ESL teacher must continue to challenge her students' learning and gain a personal grasp of what goes on in the classroom. During the instructional procedure and education.

Training transfer methods are no longer reliable for both teachers and students, as pragmatic pedagogy has become increasingly important in education. It is important to create strategies that allow educators and learners to collaborate on the learning process (Pani, 2004). Additionally, scholars have stressed the significance of "beginning with one's own experience" in teaching generally (Reinharz, 1992). and in the development of liberal education in particular (Reinharz, 1992) (Freire, 1970) Clarifying beliefs, principles, and values can be an ongoing focus of. teacher development programs, so emphasizing subjective descriptions of the principles that underlie teaching practice is important for teaching and it provides an important perspective on what is and how people acquire the ability to teach. Recent teacher education research focuses on practitioners' personal educational knowledge and informed teacher-teaching practices. As a result, teacher education programs based on this emic (insider or practitioner) perspective

seem more appropriate for finding answers to a variety of questions that arise from classroom experience.

How should future research on human resource development be conducted? Stated differently, what are our plans for upcoming professional development initiatives? In order to assist in shaping education, future research should first take into account the views of practitioners (many conflicting perspectives). Professional development programs and educational practices need to be developed or altered. All things considered, the well-known current literature in the field of teaching second or foreign languages to teachers signifies a subtle move towards scholarly, rigorous investigation and comprehension of local, personal, and societal aspects that have been overlooked in earlier studies. Throughout this process, each teacher's unique teaching ideas and approaches are examined and tested to see how well it work for them—not the other way around. This new knowledge of the post-method condition has given rise to innovative curricula, such as Teacher Training Programs, in both schools and other settings. For instance, a monolithic, specialization-seeking approach to knowledge in English teaching techniques has replaced numerous post-methodological achievements, such as multidisciplinary curricula and research. (Hatch, Shirai & Fantuzzi, 1996; Kumaravadivelu 2001). In the words of Kumaravadivelu (2001), such a perspective allows English teachers to theorize from practice and practice what they theorize by liberating individuals from their traditional understanding of knowledge production. It aims to enable students to build their own contextual pedagogical knowledge.

For educators who are just starting out in the field, training in specialized methods, procedures, and tactics will probably be crucial because it will provide them the self-assurance to deal with pupils and educate them on effective lesson-delivery skills (Richards and Rodgers, 2014). However, a developing critical perspective on teacher education points to a paradigm shift wherein a model of professional growth based on reflective practice is anticipated to replace the transmission (i.e., inadequacies) model (Arikan, 2006). The demands of practitioners that are distinctive to their contexts are highlighted by this collaborative planning (O'Connor, 2000; Purkey & Smith, 1983). For less experienced teachers, the approach or offered method, along with its related activities, ideas, and procedures, might be a vital beginning point, and it should be recognized as such, as Richards and Rodgers (2014) correctly point out. Furthermore, as teacher's expertise and knowledge grow, they start to create customized teaching strategies that draw from tried-and-true techniques while also incorporating their own values, experiences, and beliefs. Expanding programs for professional development and teacher education is essential to support newly hired teachers. instructors in making the shift from employing tried-and-true methods and strategies to creating and utilizing their own toolkit of methodological ideas and procedures.

This trip can be seen as a liberation exercise from a critical standpoint, and the freedom to self-determination is likewise denied to instructors by any program of study that overlooks the possibility of subject emancipation through knowledge obfuscation. According to Kincheloe (1995), teacher preparation that disregards freedom issues gets sucked up into the school sea and fails to recognize the rainbow of activities that go place underwater. Models enable us to explore our collective consciousness and gain fresh insight into the reality that these professional development programs attempt to imitate. This inexorably results in modifications to our methods of instruction.

CONCLUSION

Learning a language invites educators and learners to explore the vast and intriguing world of limitless opportunities. In order to travel a satisfying path for both teachers and learners in the post-method era, educators must be aware of specific ways in addition to the essential elements mentioned above. Teachers and students need to be active participants in the creation of knowledge as a result of the transition from method-based to post-method classroom practices. Teachers are no longer restricted to selecting tactics from several frameworks. Rather, it would be ideal to urge students to go out on a journey that touches on their identity, context, emotional and cognitive factors, and crucial ELT methods. Rather than dictating to their pupils what to do, educators should get to know them better and help them choose their goals. This allows both teachers and students to make the best possible decisions. And if you make a mistake, you can always go back and try again.

In order to demonstrate that all educational processes are flexible and that real-world circumstances are a result of the experiences that teachers and students have on a daily basis, post-methodical pedagogy aims to facilitate realistic educational practices. Alternatives to education are intriguing because they cannot be artificially planned and created in a vacuum. Post-method education promotes a comprehensive education where students' needs and life experiences serve as the main source of knowledge and instructional resources. The teacher's job is not limited to finding, observing, assessing, and incorporating these experiences into creative and significant learning activities. It also means that teachers take responsibility for their own professional development and social engagement, as factors such as lack of training, experience and knowledge of local conditions can hinder their work. As a result, teachers must constantly reflect, critique, evaluate and redefine their personal teaching practices in order to implement teaching practices that adequately meet the needs, opportunities, and expectations of their students.

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